

SOME PROBLEMS OF DEVELOPMENT OF MARKETING ACTIVITIES AND WAYS TO SOLVE THEM

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ABSTRACT

This article provides information on some problems of marketing development and ways to solve them, as well as problems and obstacles in the implementation of measures aimed at marketing development.

Due to the fact that marketing is a relatively new activity, there are many tasks that need to be solved before it. In the work of marketing bodies, vices such as parallelism, repetition and localism are often found. The reasons for the multi-level structure of marketing, the emergence of marketing departments in each organization or their non-organization at all have not been substantiated, analyzed and studied. There is still no body to manage and coordinate the national economy and marketing at the country level. Marketing departments have not yet been established in some ministries. The structural structure of organized marketing departments and groups is sometimes not the same in companies producing the same product. In their composition, sometimes unnecessary and redundant departments and groups are organized. In some cases, their regulations and functions have not yet been developed.

Marketing planning is still often done by hand. Sometimes it is not felt that the calculations are based on science. In fact, it is clear that most of the norms and regulations are determined in the air, taken from the air, in the style of statistics. For example, determining the need for goods is determined by multiplying the consumption rate of a person by the number of people. In this case, the norms are calculated by using consumption norms for some goods in previous years. Statistical calculation of the need is determined without any scientific basis by multiplying the amount of consumption in previous years by the coefficient of some possible changes.^[4]

The marketing infrastructure is not sufficiently developed. It is related to the production of infrastructure, different from social infrastructures, the implementation of the marketing process and the creation of conditions for it. It includes areas that are busy with

creating conditions for marketing management, such as constructions, roads, cultural and household sectors, communication. They include various software packages, information transmission, processing, storage equipment, scientific and technical tools, etc. The marketing information system is still not perfect. Their collection mainly depends on subjective circumstances. Indeed, if, for example, you need information about the demand for a product or a competitor in the market, you should certainly conduct questionnaire surveys. This is determined by the situation, character, and mood of those who answer the questionnaire and those who conduct it. Their cultural, scientific, social, political and economic level also plays a big role.

In our republic, there is no nationwide market and conjunctural data bank, although many countries have transferred this work to computers, and all the necessary information is stored in the machine's memory, processed and transferred to the right place. Operational organization and implementation of marketing is not sufficiently developed. Failure to quickly deliver information such as market capacity, price levels, competitors, supply and demand to marketing teams will cause them to be unable to act quickly and nimbly. This cannot ensure that the goods will be in the right place in the right amount, quality, and at the right time. Since marketing includes issues such as the creation of goods, their introduction to the market, and the life cycle in the market, the fact that they do not have a good idea about their production techniques and technology, quality and consumer properties, in many cases, causes many difficulties in these areas. . It is desirable for him to give appropriate instructions and suggestions regarding the condition of the goods, their improvement, consumption.^[2]

One of the important problems of marketing is to achieve perfection of pricing policy. It is necessary to achieve the full scientific basis of their determination, to consider the marketing strategy, to achieve their objectivity and truthfulness in accordance with the interests of each economy and the interests of the state. In this case, prices should not only be derived from the demand and supply of goods, but also the value of consumer characteristics. The problem of managing the sale of goods is especially important. Determining the most effective way to sell goods to consumers through trade, intermediaries and other channels, ensuring their direct delivery to customers reduces costs, the amount of working capital, accelerates their circulation. In this, all the demands and wishes of the buyers are fully taken into account. The existence of direct contacts between producers and consumers makes it possible to establish friendly relations between them, to provide technical, technological and financial assistance to each other when necessary. The establishment of such business relations has a positive effect on the interests of both parties.^[1]

Marketing should help solve communication problems. At this point, we understand problems such as advertising and promotion of goods, providing services, expanding participation in fairs and exhibitions, and having a brand and image of enterprises. This group of problems is really a result of our republic's lack of experience in this field due to the acceleration of the introduction of marketing into our lives in the following years and the application of its elements. When using them, there are cases of going beyond the limits and not knowing the norm. For example, cigarette advertising is completely banned in many countries, and we still advertise it, or cigarettes are advertised excessively. Many types of service (pre-sale and after-sale) remain underdeveloped. Exhibitions and fairs are held very rarely. Personnel problem is the most important problem. Training of special personnel in the

field of organization and implementation of marketing, unfortunately, has not been started in any country, including ours. However, the organization and implementation of marketing is distinguished by its complexity and many nuances in the management of certain industries and the national economy. Marketing is not only able to fully cover its costs and increase the well-being of its employees, but also to satisfy the high taste and needs of the product manufacturers, buyers, and consumers it serves, as well as their effective work. should make it possible for them to conduct This requires special intelligence, intelligence, understanding, culture and high knowledge from the marketing manager and his employees. In order to properly solve the above problems, the following should be done:

- * organization of departments, departments and groups engaged in special marketing in enterprises, ministries and higher management bodies;
- * establishment of bodies for rapid application of innovations and inventions created by special consulting centers, research laboratories, institutes to marketing, marketing management practice;
- * training special professional personnel, taking care of constantly raising their scientific and professional level;
- * financial incentives for personnel, increasing their level of interest in the results of their work;
- * organization of a good material and technical base, rapid implementation of the results of scientific and technical development in marketing management, etc.^[3]

The result of these works requires perfecting marketing, finding and implementing new methods and types of marketing, raising it to a higher level.

Conclusion:

The main drawback of the development of the marketing field is the lack of specialists in this field. Also, this field is not developing due to the lack of personnel and the lack of knowledge and skills of personnel, and because there are not enough specialists to train personnel. I would like to add that marketing development measures do not reach the lowest levels of the state, and as a result, any marketing reform does not show its effect.

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